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8086 Viva Questions

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Examiner

8086 is called a _____ bit μ P?
Justify your answer!

Question 1:

You

8086 is called a 16 bit μ P

It has a 16-bit ALU.

That means it can perform 16-bit arithmetic and logic operations in one cycle. Hence it is a 16-bit μ P.

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Examiner

Explain address bus and data bus of 8086?

Question 2:

You

8086 has a 20 bit address bus.
Hence it can access $2^{20} = 1$ MB of memory.

8086 has a 16-bit data bus. This means it can access 16-bit data in one cycle.

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Examiner

Explain clock signal of 8086?

Question 3:

You

8086 operates on a clock frequency of 5MHz-10MHz depending upon the version selected.

Clock is provided by 8284 Clock generator. We connect a crystal of 3 times the frequency, so as to produce a 33% duty cycle clock.

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Examiner

Explain Pipelining of 8086?

Question 4:

You

Fetching the next instruction while executing the current instruction is called pipelining. 8086 architecture is divided into 2 units. BIU is used for fetching and EU for execution.

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Examiner

What do you know about memory segmentation of 8086?

Question 5:

You

8086 has 4 memory segments.
Code segment stores programs.
Stack segment holds the stack.
Data segment stores data.
Extra segment also stores data.
Max size of each segment is 64KB.
Min size of each segment is 16 bytes.

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Examiner

What are segment address, offset address and physical address?

Question 6:

You

Segment address gives the 16-bit base address of the segment. When multiplied by 10, it becomes the starting address of the segment. Offset address gives the 16-bit offset within the segment.

Physical address is the 20-bit actual address of a location in the memory

It is calculated as

$\text{segment addr} \times 10\text{H} + \text{offset addr}$

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Microprocessor 8086

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Internal Examiner

Explain GPRs of 8086?

Question 7:

You

8086 has 4, 16-bit General Purpose registers: AX, BX, CX and DX.

They can also be used as 8, independent 8-bit registers: AL, AH etc. AL is the lower byte of AX and AH is the higher byte.

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Examiner

Explain status flags of 8086?

Question 8:

You

8086 has 6 status flags.

CF: 1 = Result has carry out of MSB

PF: 1 = Result has even parity

AC: 1 = Carry from lower to higher nibble

ZF: 1 = Result is zero

SF: 1 = MSB of result is 1

OV: 1 = Signed overflow

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Examiner

What is signed overflow and Overflow flag?

Question 9:

You

An 8-bit signed number must be in the range -80H ... +7FH. If the result goes beyond this range then it is called a signed overflow. In such case Overflow flag becomes 1 to indicate that Sign flag is wrong. Similarly for a 16-bit number the range is -8000H to +7FFFH

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Internal Examiner

What are control flags of 8086?

Question 10:

You

8086 has 3 control flags.

DF: 1 = Auto-decrement direction

IF: 1 = Interrupt is enabled

TF: 1 = Perform single stepping

Ref Video: 8086 | Flag Register

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What are memory banks of 8086?

Question 11:

You

8086 has 2 memory banks, so that it can transfer 16-bit data in one machine cycle.

Even bank (lower bank) and Odd bank (higher bank). Lower bank is selected when A0 is 0, higher bank is selected when BHE (bar) is 0.

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Examiner

Explain some of the main addressing modes?

Question 12:

You

Immediate: Data given in the instruction. *E.g.: MOV CL, 25H*

Register: Data given in a register. *E.g.: MOV CL, BL*

Direct: Address given in the instruction. *E.g.: MOV CL, [2000H]*

Indirect: Address given in a register. *E.g.: MOV CL, [BX]*

Implied: The operand is implied. *E.g.: STC*

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Examiner

Explain CBW instruction of 8086?

Question 13:

You

CBW converts a byte (8-bit) to a word (16-bit). The operand must be in AL and the result is produced in AX. It sign extends (Extends MSB) of AL into AH.

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Examiner

What is the difference between
SUB BL, CL and CMP BL, CL?

Question 14:

You

Both perform BL-CL.

SUB will store the result in BL and
affect the flags.

CMP will NOT STORE the result, it
will ONLY affect the flags.

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Examiner

What is the difference between ADD and ADC instructions?

Question 15:

You

Both perform addition. ADD is a half adder. ADC is a full adder, as in, it will also include the carry of the previous operation. It is used to add large numbers. It is used to add large sized numbers so that the carry of the lower byte propagates into the higher byte.

Ref Video: 8086 | Arithmetic Instrs
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Explain the following instructions:
XLAT, DAA, LOOP, MOVSB, TEST,
PUSH, IN, OUT, MUL, DIV?

Question 16:

You

Though any instruction can be asked,
the ones above are the MOST
FREQUENTLY asked instructions.
Their explanations are very long.
Refer my videos for the same at
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Examiner

What are instruction prefixes used in 8086?

Question 17:

You

3 prefixes: REP, LOCK and ESC

REP: Used to repeat string instructions

LOCK: Prevents the μ P from releasing the system bus during an instruction.

ESC: Used to identify an 8087 instruction. (Binary pattern: 11011)

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Examiner

What are the special uses of the four GPRs?

Question 18:

You

AX: Accumulator for MUL/DIV etc.

BX: Holds 16-bit memory offset address for indirect addressing mode.

CX: Holds count for LOOP, REP etc.

DX: Holds 16-bit I/O address for indirect I/O addressing mode.

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Examiner

List some important assembler directives?

Question 19:

You

Assume, Start, End, Segment, Ends, DB, DQ, DD, DUP, Offset, Org are some of the most common assembler directives.

Ref Video: 8086 | Programming Part 1
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What is the difference between RET and IRET instructions?

Question 20:

You

RET is used to return from an ordinary subroutine.

It pops only IP and CS.

IRET is used to return from an ISR.

It pops IP, CS and Flags.

Ref Video: 8086 | Interrupts

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What is segment overriding?

Question 21:

You

Changing the default segment for the operation is called segment overriding.

MOV CL, [2000H] by default operates on data segment.

MOV CL, **ES:** [2000H] by overriding, this instruction now operates on the extra segment.

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Examiner

What is the difference between a subroutine (procedure) and a macro?

Question 22:

You

When we CALL a subroutine, the program control shifts from the main program to the subroutine, and after execution, returns to the next instruction after CALL.

When we invoke a macro, the macro code is pasted into our program at the location where the macro was invoked.

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Examiner

What are the dedicated interrupts of 8086?

Question 23:

You

INT 0: Divide error

INT 1: Single Stepping

INT 2: NMI

INT 3: Breakpoint

INT 0: Interrupt on Overflow

Ref Video: 8086 | Interrupts

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Compare the hardware interrupts of 8086?

Question 24:

You

NMI: Non Maskable, Vectored, High Priority, Edge triggered.

INTR: Maskable, Non Vectored, Low Priority, Level triggered.

Ref Video: 8086 | Interrupts

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Examiner

What is the use of INTA (bar)?

Question 25:

You

INTA (bar) is given to as a response to INTR, to ask for the vector number. On 1st INTA, 8259 generates the vector number. On 2nd INTA 8259 sends the vector number.

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Internal Examiner ~ Jon Snow

What is min mode and max mode of 8086?

Question 26:

You

Min mode is a uni-processor system. 8086 is the only processor in the circuit. (MN/MX = 1)

Max mode is a multi-processor system. 8086 can be used with 8087 math co processor or 8089 I/O processor. (MN/MX = 0)

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Examiner

What is the reset vector address of 8086?

Question 27:

You

On reset CS becomes FFFFH and IP becomes 0000H hence the reset vector address is FFFF0H. μ P goes here on reset to execute the BIOS program.

Ref Video: 8086 | Memory Designing
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Explain the role of the following chips: 8282, 8284, 8286, 8288?

Question 28:

You

8282: Octal Latch

8284: Clock generator

8286: Data transreceiver

8288: Bus Controller

All of these are explained in full detail in my videos of min mode and max mode on my website

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is the role of these signals:
ALE, DEN, DT/R, RD, WR, M/IO?

Question 29:

You

ALE: Latches address

DEN: Enables transreceiver

DT/R: Decides transmit/ receive

RD: Read control signal

WR: Write control signal

M/IO: Decides memory or I/O operation

All of these are explained in full detail in my videos of min mode and max mode on my website www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

Describe 8259 PIC in brief?

Question 30:

You

Programmable interrupt controller.
Used to increase number of
interrupts. Single 8259 gives 8
interrupts, cascaded gives 64 max.
Has fixed and rotating priority. Allows
Edge and level triggers. Allows
individual masking of interrupts.

Ref Video: 8259 | Architecture
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Describe 8255 PPI in brief?

Question 31:

You

Programmable peripheral interface.
Provides 3, 8-bit interface ports
between μ P and I/O devices.
Has 3 operating modes.
Performs handshaking for reliable
data transfers. Has BSR feature to
control port C lines individually.

Ref Video: 8255 | Architecture

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Describe 8253/8254 PIT in brief?

Question 32:

You

Programmable interval timer.

Has 3, 16bit down counters.

Can operate in 6 different modes.

Allows Latching of count.

Can emulate IC555 as a mono stable multi vibrator.

Ref Video: 8253/54 | Architecture

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

Explain 8237/8257 DMAC in brief?

Question 33:

You

DMA controller.

Transfers data between memory and I/O. Has 4 channels. Has fixed and rotating priority. Can perform Cycle stealing, block transfer, DMA read, DMA Write and DMA verify cycles. Has a 14 bit count.

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Examiner

What is memory mapped I/O and I/O mapped I/O?

Question 34:

You

Memory mapped I/O: I/O devices mapped into memory space just like memory devices.

I/O mapped I/O also called isolated I/O: I/O devices mapped into a separate I/O space.

There is a special video on just this topic at my website:

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Examiner

What is the use of AND, OR, XOR instructions?

Question 35:

You

AND: To clear a bit from a register.

OR: To set a bit from a register.

XOR: To complement a bit from a register.

There is a special video on just this topic at my website:

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Examiner

What is an instruction cycle,
machine cycle and T-state?

Question 36:

You

Instruction cycle: Total process of fetching, decoding and executing an instruction. **Machine cycle:** One complete operation of the system bus. **T-state:** One clock cycle.

Instruction cycle has several machine cycles. Machine cycle has 4 T-states. Watch the video on timing diagrams
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

AL has a value 35H. How can you make it 53H?

Question 37:

You

Rotate AL 4 times in any direction, the nibbles will get interchanged.

Code:

```
MOV CL, 04H
```

```
ROL AL, CL
```

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Examiner

What is aligned and misaligned data?

Question 38:

You

If 16bit data begins at even address it is aligned. Else misaligned. Only aligned data can be transferred in one cycle.

Ref topic: Memory banking for more at:
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What are the variable sizes in 8086 assembly language programming?

Question 39:

You

DB: 8-bit.

DW: 16-bit.

DD: 32-bit.

DQ: 64-bit.

DT: 80-bit.

Ref: Programming 1st video at:

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is EOI command in 8259?

Question 40:

You

EOI is end of interrupt. It is a command given at the end of the ISR to inform 8259 that the ISR is completed hence it must reset the bit in In Service Register.

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Examiner

What are ICWs and OCWs of 8259?

Question 41:

You

ICWs are Initialization command words
And OCWs are operational command words. These are commands used to program 8259 as per the users requirement of masking, triggering, priority, cascading etc.

Ref Video: 8259 | ICWs and OCWs
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is BSR command of 8255?

Question 42:

You

Bit Set Reset is a command by which the programmer can set or reset individual lines of PC without affecting any other line.

There is a special video on just this topic at my website:

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Bharat Acharya Education

Examiner

Name input and output handshake signals?

Question 43:

You

Input handshake signals:

STB: Strobe

IBF: Input Buffer Full

There is a special video on just this topic at my website:

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Examiner

Name the timer modes of
8253/8254 PIT?

Question 44:

You

M0: Interrupt on TC

M1: Mono-stable Multi-vibrator

M2: Rate Generator

M3: Square Wave Generator

M4: Software Triggered Strobe

M5: Hardware Triggered Strobe

Ref Video: 8253 | Timer Modes

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Examiner

Compare SRAM and DRAM memories briefly?

Question 45:

You

SRAM: Uses Flip Flops, Faster, Expensive, No Refreshing Needed.

DRAM: Uses Capacitor, Slower, Cheaper, Refreshing Needed via 8203 DRAM Controller.

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Examiner

Compare 8088 and 8086 microprocessors briefly?

Question 46:

You

8088: 8-bit data bus, no banking, 4 byte queue, no BHE signal, slower.

8086: 16-bit data bus, banking, 6 byte queue, BHE signal present, faster.

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Examiner

What is the use of READY signal
in 8086 μ P?

Question 47:

You

READY is used to synchronize the μ P
with slower devices.

μ P checks READY in every cycle. IF
READY = 0 μ P enters Wait State and
only comes out of it when READY
becomes 1, giving the device time to
get ready for the operation.

Ref Video: 8086 Minimum Mode

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is the use of TEST (bar) signal in 8086 μ P?

Question 48:

You

It is used to synchronize 8086 with 8087 NDP. It is connected with the BUSY signal of 8087. If Busy = 1, 8086 will enter wait state and will resume when BUSY is 0.

Ref Video: 8086-8087 Interfacing
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is the use of DUP and OFFSET assembler directives in 8086?

Question 49:

You

DUP | Duplicate
Used to create an Array

OFFSET
Used to obtain Offset address from the assembler

Ref Video: 8086 | Palindrome Program
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What are the string instructions of
8086 μ P?

Question 50:

You

MOVS
LODS
STOS
CMPS
SCAS

Ref Video: 8086 | String Instructions
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is the use of INT 21H?

Question 51:

You

INT 21H is a DOS interrupt. It is used to invoke several DOS functions like accepting a value from the user, displaying the result on the screen, terminating the program etc.

Ref Video: 8086 | INT 21H

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Examiner

Describe any sorting method in assembly programming?

Question 52:

You

Bubble Sort

Algorithm: Compare two adjacent numbers. If they are in correct order then leave them else interchange them. Do it in a nested loop with count (N-1). By the end the series is sorted!

Ref Video: 8086 | Sorting Program

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

What is the use of advance write signals AMWTC & AIOWC in 8086?

Question 53:

You

The advanced write signals get activated (low) one T-state in advance as compared to the normal write signals. This gives slow devices extra time to get ready and hence reduces the chances of adding extra Wait States.

Ref Video: 8086 | Minimum Mode
www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

How do you SET the Trap Flag in
8086 μ P?

Question 54:

You

```
PUSHF
POP BX
OR BH, 01H
PUSH BX
POPF
```

Video Ref: 8086 | Processor Control Instrs

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

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Examiner

Compare software delay and hardware delays?

Question 55:

You

Software delay | Produced by a program, cheaper, more flexible, keeps μ P busy

Hardware delay | Produced by a timer, costlier, less flexible, keeps μ P free

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Examiner

What is the use of INT 21H?

Question 56:

You

INT 21h is a DOS interrupt. It is used to invoke several DOS functions like accepting a value from the user, displaying the result on the screen, terminating the program etc.

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Examiner

What are the various types of Indirect addressing modes?

Question 57:

You

Register Indirect

E.g.:: MOV CL, [BX]

Register Relative

E.g.:: MOV CL, [BX+03H]

Base Indexed

E.g.:: MOV CL, [BX+SI]

Base Relative Plus Indexed

E.g.:: MOV CL, [BX+SI+05H]

Ref Video: 8086 | Addressing Modes

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What are the various operating modes of 8259 PIC?

Question 58:

You

Priority Modes:

FNM, SFNM, Rotating Priority.

EOI Modes:

Normal EOI, Auto EOI

Other Modes:

SMM, Poll Mode, Buffered Mode

Ref Video: 8259 | Operating Modes

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

In Loop Instruction, how many Iterations will we get for these counts 0001H, 0010H, FFFFH, 0000H?

Question 59:

You

Count: 0001H | Iterations: 1

Count: 0010H | Iterations: 16

Count: FFFFH | Iterations: 65535

Count: 0000H | Iterations: 65536

Ref Video: 8086 | Branch Instrs

www.BharatAcharyaEducation.com

Examiner

What is the use of $\overline{\text{RQ}} / \overline{\text{GT}}$ signal of 8086 μ P?

Question 60:

You

Request/ Grant signals are used by other processors to take control of the system bus from 8086 in max mode. $\overline{\text{RQ}} / \overline{\text{GT}} 0$ is higher priority than $\overline{\text{RQ}} / \overline{\text{GT}} 1$.

Ref Video: 8086 | Maximum Mode
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